

LIBRARY SATISFACTION, LIBRARY PREFERENCE AND LIBRARY UTILIZATION OF COLLEGE STUDENTS IN ST. PETER'S COLLEGE OF TORIL, INC.

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Library Satisfaction, Library Preference and Library Utilization of College Students in St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc.

Earl Benedict A. Bawasanta,* Jeraldine F. Apal, Mae A. Bolasa, Julia Claire A. Lumanta,
Kenneth Mesario, Emmanuel L. Templa, Katherine Rosales

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study examines the influence of library satisfaction and preference on the library utilization of college students at St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. It aims to assess students' satisfaction with the library's facilities, services, and resources, as well as their preferences, attitudes, and perceived value of the library in relation to their usage. Using a quantitative descriptive-correlational design, data was collected through an online survey from 275 college students enrolled in the school year 2023-2024. Findings reveal that students report high satisfaction with the library's facilities, services, and resources and show a strong preference for the library, recognizing its importance in their academic experience. However, weak positive correlations were found between satisfaction, preference, and actual library utilization, suggesting that other factors may contribute to library use beyond these variables. The study concludes that while students value the library, further research is needed to identify additional factors influencing its utilization. Understanding these factors can help enhance library services and better meet students' academic needs.

Keywords: *library satisfaction, library preference, library utilization, correlational study, college student*

Introduction

The library has long been recognized as an essential resource for students' learning and academic success (Egwuonwu et al., 2022). As a vital component of any educational institution, it provided access to critical information and learning materials, supporting students' academic journeys. However, despite its significance, school libraries often faced low utilization rates due to challenges such as limited funding, inadequate facilities, and substandard services (Soulen & Tedrow, 2021). These issues, though varying across institutions, commonly related to students' satisfaction with library services and their preferences for using the library as an information source. This study examined the influence of students' satisfaction, preferences, and overall library utilization within the college department. Library utilization encompassed the recorded use of information resources by students, teachers, staff, and administrators (Ani et al., 2022), including services like consultation, reference, and book borrowing.

User satisfaction, a key factor in evaluating library effectiveness, referred to users' assessments of whether library resources and services met their academic needs (Awotona & Ipadeola, 2019). High satisfaction rates increased the likelihood of continued library use, emphasizing the importance of regular evaluations to improve services. Academic libraries frequently employed user surveys to measure satisfaction, ensuring that services aligned with students' evolving needs (Atuase & Koufie, 2017). Improving services based on user feedback aligned with the library's primary goal of maximizing user engagement (Mawia, 2021). Additionally, library preference—defined as students' interest in selecting the library as a preferred learning space—varied among users. Kim (2017) found that many students used the library during non-class hours for studying or leisure, reflecting the library's continued relevance in academic life.

Numerous studies highlighted the strong correlation between service quality and library utilization. Gyau et al. (2021) emphasized that enhancing service quality significantly increased user satisfaction. Hughes (2020) found that libraries were heavily used during exam periods for studying and accessing academic materials, while Abassi et al. (2020) stressed the importance of diverse study spaces—such as quiet zones, open areas, and private rooms—in boosting library use. Zoss (2021) noted that failing to meet students' needs for conducive study environments could lead to a decline in library visits. In the Philippine context, Dagdag and Galiza (2020) observed that book collections and library services directly influenced student satisfaction and use, while Dupa et al. (2018) highlighted the need for upgraded book collections to support academic needs. Despite the growing preference for digital resources (Bollido et al., 2019), many students still valued the library for its physical study spaces and diverse collections.

At St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc., a decline in library visits raised concerns about underutilization. Institutional records showed a 19.75% drop in student visits, from 12,217 in the 2018-2019 academic year to 9,804 in 2022-2023. This decline reflected broader trends influenced by factors such as outdated materials (Cuenca, 2020), limited operating hours, and the increased reliance on online resources (Surmieda, 2011). The COVID-19 pandemic further reduced physical library use as students turned to digital platforms (Libraries and the Pandemic, 2023). This study explored the factors behind the decline, focusing on students' satisfaction, preferences, and utilization patterns. The findings aimed to inform strategies for enhancing library services, fostering student engagement, and promoting academic success at St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc.

Research Questions

This study explores the level of satisfaction and preference and their influence on library utilization among college students at St.

Peter's College of Toril, Inc., for the school year 2023-2024. It seeks to explore whether a significant influence exists between satisfaction, library utilization, and preference. Finally, this study aims to determine which satisfaction and preference significantly influence library utilization. Mainly, this study answers the following research questions:

1. What is the level of library satisfaction of college students? Specifically in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender; and
 - 1.3. level of technological skills?
2. What is the level of library preference of college students? Specifically in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. relevance of library;
 - 2.2. attitude towards library use; and
 - 2.3. valuation of the library?
3. What is the level of library utilization of college students? Specifically in terms of the following:
 - 3.1. frequency of library use?
4. Is there a significant influence on library satisfaction and library utilization?
5. Is there a significant influence on library preference and library utilization?
6. Which of the two independent variables significantly influences library utilization?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design, specifically a descriptive-correlational approach, to analyze statistical data and determine the relationships between variables. Descriptive research aimed to gather detailed and accurate information, while correlational studies focused on understanding the connections among variables (Stangor & Walinga, 2019). The research investigated the significant influence of three variable level of satisfaction, level of preference, and level of library utilization—and aimed to identify which independent variable had the most substantial impact on the dependent variable. This approach facilitated a comprehensive examination of the relationships among the variables within the study.

Respondents

This study at St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. for the 2023-2024 school year utilized random sampling to ensure equal opportunity for college students to participate as respondents. As Taylor (2023) noted, random sampling is a widely used technique in research that allows for the selection of participants from the entire college population. A sample size of 275 out of 457 students was determined to ensure generalized and authentic results. Participation in the study was voluntary, and the confidentiality of responses was maintained in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The researchers believed that these 275 students represented the various college departments and would provide unbiased and comprehensive results for interpretation.

Instrument

This study assessed the influence of satisfaction and preference on library utilization among college students using a researcher-constructed online survey questionnaire comprising three sections: satisfaction, preference, and utilization. Each independent variable included fifteen Likert-scale questions, ranging from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree," to evaluate students' perceptions of the college library, while the dependent variable measured library visit frequency, from "Always" (21 visits and above) to "Rarely" (0–5 visits).

The survey instrument was designed to align with the study's objectives, directly addressing the statement of the problem and gathering relevant data. To ensure validity and reliability, experts evaluated the instrument before pilot testing it with 30 college students from St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc., conducted online via Google Forms. The pilot test results were subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding values of .830 for "Facility in General," .855 for "Services Offered," and .905 for "Collection and Resources" under Library Satisfaction. For Library Preference, the indicators showed alpha values of .901 for "Relevance of Library," .930 for "Attitude Towards Library," and .924 for "Valuation Towards Library." These results confirmed that all items were good and reliable, strengthening the study's findings on the relationship between satisfaction, preference, and library utilization.

Procedure

The researcher will request permission from the school president to conduct a study on The Library Satisfaction and Preference and Their Influence on the Library Utilization of College Students in St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. Random sampling will be employed for data collection, with the primary aim of engaging college major club presidents to facilitate survey distribution. During the administration of survey questionnaires, the researchers will secure precise arrangements and agreements with the presidents through verbal verification before creating a group chat and disseminating the online research instrument. Data compilation and organization will be conducted using Google Forms and Excel, ensuring efficient management and quality control. Subsequently, the researchers will conclude and provide insightful interpretations of the data.

Data Analysis

To investigate the impact of library satisfaction and preference on utilization, researchers utilized Mean Score and Standard Deviation to measure average satisfaction and variability among responses. The researchers also employed Pearson's Correlation Coefficient to examine the relationship between these variables, suggesting that satisfaction could influence library usage frequency. Linear Regression was later used to pinpoint which variable, satisfaction, or preference, significantly affects library utilization. This multifaceted approach allowed for a detailed analysis of factors influencing students' library usage. The study aims to offer precise insights and recommendations for enhancing library services through these statistical tools.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers adhered to ethical guidelines by ensuring voluntary participation and obtaining informed consent from respondents. Participants have the right to refuse or withdraw from the study without repercussions. Privacy and confidentiality were diligently maintained to mitigate potential risks. The research aimed to inform educational decisions, aid teacher development, improve student learning outcomes, foster a positive school environment, and contribute to academic research. Transparent sharing of study results will be facilitated and accessible to all interested parties.

Results and Discussion

Level of Library Satisfaction

The following table shows the result of every statement/question provided per indicator regarding the Level of Satisfaction of the College Students. The results are the following:

Table 1. *Level of Library Satisfaction Overall Result Mean and SD: Facility in General*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I am satisfied with the library's available tools and equipment (e.g., computers).	4.05	0.853	High
I am satisfied with the available study spaces in the library.	4.29	0.847	Very High
I am satisfied with the available library collection and resources.	4.11	0.828	High
I am satisfied with the conducive space inside the library for research.	4.16	0.858	High
I am satisfied with the overall quality and functionality of various library facilities.	4.14	0.864	High
Indicator's Mean	4.15	0.853	High

The survey results indicate that college students are highly satisfied with the library's study spaces, reflected by a mean score of 4.29 (SD = 0.847) for the statement, "I am satisfied with the available study spaces in the library." This aligns with Rai and Zaveri (2022), who highlighted the critical role of academic spaces in enhancing library value. Physical facilities significantly influence user satisfaction, as noted by Iwhiwhu and Okorodudu (2012), who emphasized the importance of well-designed study areas, seating, and accessibility features in fostering a conducive learning environment. Similarly, Mani et al. (2019) found that students are more likely to utilize library spaces perceived as comfortable and functional. Conversely, satisfaction with the library's tools and equipment, such as computers, received a slightly lower mean score of 4.05 (SD = 0.853), though still reflecting high satisfaction. This supports Thompson's (2012) view that the availability of desktop computers promotes frequent library visits, while Yap et al. (2022) emphasized that user satisfaction also depends on diverse information resources and essential equipment. The overall average satisfaction rating of 4.15 underscores the combined value of study spaces, tools, and resources in meeting student needs and promoting library utilization.

These findings highlight that library satisfaction is multifaceted, shaped by the integration of facilities, resources, and services. Grounded in the Expectancy-Value Theory (Drew, 2023), students are more likely to use the library when its offerings align with their expectations and perceived value. The SERVQUAL Model (Bhasin, 2023) further reinforces that the consistent delivery of quality facilities and equipment fosters user satisfaction and loyalty. High-quality services—such as lending, internet access, and staff support—also play a crucial role in shaping user experiences, as emphasized by Awotona and Ipadeola (2019) and Musa and Olawale (2023). Continuous improvements in these areas can strengthen library engagement, solidifying its role as a vital academic resource.

Table 2. *Level of Library Satisfaction Overall Result Mean and SD: Services Offered*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I am satisfied with the courtesy and availability of library staff assistance.	4.28	0.824	Very High
I am satisfied with the sufficient research tools like computers and internet connection.	3.92	0.940	High
I am satisfied with the efficiency of the book loan process (reserving and renewing).	4.16	0.842	High
I am satisfied with sufficient guidance and user training services.	4.17	0.841	High
I am satisfied with the librarian's professional knowledge.	4.36	0.814	Very High
Indicator's Mean	4.18	0.865	High

The survey results reveal that college students are highly satisfied with the librarian's professional knowledge, reflected by the highest mean score of 4.36 (SD = 0.814) for the statement, "I am satisfied with the librarian's professional knowledge." This underscores strong student appreciation for the expertise and professionalism of library staff. Ekeng and Esin (2021) emphasized that dissatisfaction with staff behavior can undermine a library's core purpose, while Awotona and Ipadeola (2019) highlighted the importance of librarian competence and approachability in fostering positive user experiences. When librarians provide accurate information, guidance, and efficient services, students are more likely to engage with library resources regularly. In contrast, the statement, "I am satisfied with the sufficient research tools like computers and internet connection," received the lowest mean score of 3.92 (SD = 0.940), though it still reflects high satisfaction. This points to a crucial area for improvement, as Singh and Sharma (2021) stressed the growing importance of reliable internet access in enabling students to explore global information resources. Similarly, Yap et al. (2022) noted that user satisfaction is closely tied to the availability and reliability of essential academic tools like high-speed internet and computers, with limitations in these resources potentially reducing student engagement.

The total indicator mean of 4.18 (SD = 0.865) reflects a high level of satisfaction with library services, though the need to improve internet connectivity and computer availability remains evident. This finding aligns with the Expectancy-Value Theory (Atkinson, 1950; Drew, 2023), which suggests that users are more motivated to engage when their expectations are met and they perceive value in the experience. The SERVQUAL Model (Bhasin, 2023) further emphasizes that addressing gaps in tangible resources enhances user satisfaction and fosters loyalty. Supporting this, Rodrigues and Mandrekar (2020) noted that evolving library facilities to meet user needs leads to increased utilization. By enhancing essential tools while maintaining high service quality, the library can strengthen its role as a vital academic support facility, ultimately driving greater student engagement and satisfaction.

Table 3. Level of Library Satisfaction Overall Result Mean and SD: Collection and Resource

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
I am satisfied with the sufficiency and variety of library collections and resources.	4.19	0.788	High
I am satisfied with the accessibility of the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC).	4.08	0.842	High
I am satisfied with the relevant and up-to-date book collections and resources.	4.11	0.885	High
I am satisfied with how the materials are organized in the library.	4.27	0.806	Very High
I am satisfied with the accessibility of subscribed online databases and outside resources.	4.08	0.852	High
Indicator's Mean	4.15	0.837	High

The research findings reveal that college students are most satisfied with the organization of library materials, as shown by the highest mean score of 4.27 (SD = 0.806) for the statement, "I am satisfied with how the materials are organized in the library." This highlights students' strong appreciation for the efficient arrangement of resources, which supports Olise's (2021) assertion that well-organized materials significantly enhance user satisfaction and library utilization. A systematic layout enables students to easily locate resources, fostering greater library use and supporting academic success. Rodrigues and Mandrekar (2020) further emphasized that a structured library environment directly correlates with increased user engagement and the perceived value of library services. However, slightly lower satisfaction levels were noted in digital resource accessibility. Both the statement on the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) and the accessibility of subscribed online databases recorded a mean score of 4.08 (SD = 0.842), indicating high but less optimal satisfaction. Cabonero et al. (2020) highlighted that OPAC's efficiency directly influences user satisfaction, while Yap et al. (2022) stressed the growing importance of accessible digital resources in meeting evolving academic demands.

With an overall mean satisfaction score of 4.15 (SD = 0.837), the findings indicate general contentment with library resources but also highlight the need to improve digital accessibility. This aligns with the Expectancy-Value Theory (Atkinson, 1950; Drew, 2023), which posits that students are more likely to utilize library resources when their expectations for accessibility and organization are met. Inefficiencies in digital tools like OPAC and online databases may reduce the library's perceived value, leading to decreased usage. Conversely, enhancing these services can increase engagement and student satisfaction. The SERVQUAL Model (Bhasin, 2023) reinforces this, emphasizing the importance of aligning library services with user expectations across reliability, responsiveness, and tangibles. Strengthening digital resource accessibility will enhance these service dimensions, ensuring the library remains a vital academic support hub capable of meeting the evolving needs of its users.

Table 4. Overall Level of Satisfaction of College Students

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description
Facility in General	4.15	0.853	High
Services Offered	4.18	0.865	High
Collection and Resource	4.15	0.837	High
Variable's Mean	4.16	0.279	High

The study highlights college students' overall satisfaction with the library's facilities, services, and resources. The facility received a high satisfaction rating (M = 4.15, SD = 0.853), supporting Rodrigues and Mandrekar's (2020) view that well-maintained facilities

enhance user experiences and library utilization. Conversely, Ekeng and Esin (2021) warned that poor facility conditions could undermine the library's purpose, emphasizing the need for continuous improvement. Library services also scored highly ($M = 4.18$, $SD = 0.865$), reflecting the value of organized materials and responsive staff, as noted by Olise (2021). Iwhiwhu and Okorodudu (2012) stressed that efficient services improve academic experiences, while Ekeng and Esin (2021) highlighted the impact of professional staff behavior on user satisfaction. The collection and resources indicator showed a similar satisfaction level ($M = 4.15$, $SD = 0.837$), though minor gaps were noted in the accessibility of the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) and external databases. Cabonero et al. (2020) emphasized OPAC's role in navigating collections, while Yap et al. (2022) stressed the need for accessible digital resources. The overall satisfaction mean of 4.16 ($SD = 0.279$) reflects strong student approval, aligning with Aragaw's (2015) assertion that user-centered libraries enhance institutional value.

These findings align with the Expectancy-Value Theory (Atkinson, 1950; Drew, 2023), which posits that users engage more when their expectations are met and they perceive value in their actions. The consistently high satisfaction rates suggest that the library successfully meets these expectations, encouraging sustained engagement. The SERVQUAL Model (Bhasin, 2023) further explains this by highlighting service quality dimensions—reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles—that drive user satisfaction. The library's strengths in tangibles (facilities and resources) and reliability (service consistency) contribute to its success. However, Singh and Sharma (2021) emphasized that enhancing digital services, especially OPAC and internet connectivity, remains crucial in the digital age. Addressing these gaps can further strengthen the library's role as a central academic support hub, fostering deeper student engagement and satisfaction.

Level of Library Preference

The following table shows the result of every statement/question provided per indicator regarding the Level of Preference of College Students. The results are the following:

Table 5. *Level of Library Preference Overall Result Mean and SD: Relevance of Library*

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The library's resources and materials can meet my educational needs and contribute to my growth.	4.27	0.801	Very High
The information provided by the library helps me improve my habit of self-study.	4.21	0.827	Very High
The library provides adequate resources for my information searches.	4.25	0.809	Very High
The library is essential to my academic journey and helps me stay updated with my studies.	4.30	0.754	Very High
The library helps develop my knowledge and skills through reading materials.	4.32	0.763	Very High
Indicator's Mean	4.27	0.791	Very High

The study revealed that statement no. 5, highlighting the library's role in developing knowledge and skills through reading materials, received the highest mean value of 4.32 ($SD = 0.760$), indicating college students' strong preference for the library as a key contributor to academic growth. Itsekor and Nwokeoma (2017) emphasized libraries' role in fostering a reading culture and personal development, while Kim (2017) noted that libraries remain preferred spaces for students due to their adaptability and resource availability. Statement no. 2, focusing on improving self-study habits, followed closely with a mean of 4.21 ($SD = 0.827$), aligning with Pagalilauan et al. (2023), who highlighted libraries' role in promoting intellectual growth, and Behera (2017), who stressed the value of library resources in supporting academic success. The overall mean of 4.27 ($SD = 0.791$) reflects consistently high student preference, shaped by the library's functional role and the perceived value of its resources. Ganguly and Bhasin (2019) further noted that students' positive attitudes toward library use are influenced by perceptions of relevance and accessibility.

These findings align with the Expectancy-Value Theory (Drew, 2023), suggesting that students view library use as instrumental to academic success when their expectations of utility are met. The library's support for knowledge development and self-study reinforces its value as an essential academic resource. The SERVQUAL Model (Bhasin, 2023) further explains this high satisfaction, highlighting how the library meets user expectations across service quality dimensions, fostering loyalty and continued engagement. Moreover, students' preferences are shaped by their perceptions of library spaces, resources, and services. Rodrigues and Mandrekar (2020) noted that students often use libraries for specific services like consulting periodicals or photocopying, while flexible offerings encourage broader patronage. Lizazi-Mbanga and Mapulanga (2021) also emphasized that cultural backgrounds and individual needs influence library usage patterns, underscoring the importance of recognizing diverse preferences to promote sustained utilization and deeper academic engagement.

The results in table 6 reveal a strong preference among college students for utilizing the library and its facilities for academic tasks. Statements like "I prefer to utilize the library and its facilities for my studies and other academic tasks" and "I prefer to study in the library because I have a positive attitude toward using it" both achieved the highest mean value of 4.25, with standard deviations of 0.743 and 0.818, respectively. These findings highlight students' positive perceptions of the library as a conducive learning space, consistent with Kim (2017), who emphasized libraries' adaptability and role in fostering long-term engagement. Itsekor and Nwokeoma (2017) similarly noted the library's contribution to information dissemination, communication, and personal development by promoting

a reading culture. Although slightly lower, statements about regular visits and maximizing library resources scored mean values of 4.19, suggesting that while students value the library, factors like study habits and time constraints may influence usage frequency. Pagalilauan et al. (2023) emphasized that regular library use strengthens academic engagement and study habits. The overall indicator mean of 4.22 reflects a generally high preference and positive attitude toward library use, reinforcing its role as an essential academic resource and aligning with the Expectancy-Value Theory (Drew, 2023), which posits that students are more motivated to use resources they find beneficial for academic success.

Table 6. Level of Library Preference Overall Result Mean and SD: Attitudes towards Library Use

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
I prefer to utilize the library and its facilities for my studies and other academic tasks.	4.25	0.743	Very High
I regularly visit the library for academic tasks like studying, coursework, and research.	4.19	0.800	High
I prefer to maximize the use of the library and its available resources and services.	4.19	0.808	High
I prefer to use the library because the library is an integral part of my journey as a student.	4.24	0.801	Very High
I prefer to study in the library because I have a positive attitude toward using it.	4.25	0.818	Very High
Indicator's Mean	4.22	0.794	Very High

The SERVQUAL Model further contextualizes these findings by focusing on service quality and user satisfaction. Bhasin (2023) highlights that user satisfaction increases when services meet expectations, a view echoed by Ganguly and Bhasin (2019), who noted that students' library engagement is shaped by perceptions of relevance, service quality, and accessibility. Omeluzor et al. (2013) and Cha and Kim (2015) further stressed the importance of flexible spaces, technology integration, and community engagement in maintaining student interest. Lizazi-Mbanga and Mapulanga (2021) added that students' cultural backgrounds and academic needs influence usage patterns. Collectively, these findings emphasize the need for libraries to continuously adapt services to align with evolving student expectations, fostering sustained academic engagement and meaningful library use

Table 7. Level of Library Preference Overall Result Mean and SD: Valuation of the Library

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
The library is a very important learning facility for teachers.	4.49	0.706	Very High
I recognize the benefits the library provides to me and the other students.	4.43	0.733	Very High
The library's value in helping me widen the scope of my knowledge.	4.34	0.758	Very High
I recognize the value of the library for the students' and teachers' persona and professional development.	4.42	0.707	Very High
The library is a valuable help in enhancing my skills and knowledge.	4.41	0.736	Very High
Indicator's Mean	4.42	0.729	Very High

The results indicate that the library plays a vital role in student and teacher learning, with Statement 1 achieving a high indicator mean value of 4.49 (SD = 0.706), reflecting a strong preference for the library as an essential resource for knowledge acquisition. This aligns with Kim (2017), who emphasized the library's adaptability and its role as a supportive learning environment fostering academic engagement. Itsekor and Nwokeoma (2017) similarly highlighted the library's role in promoting information dissemination, communication, and personal development, nurturing a reading culture essential for academic success. Statement 3, with a mean of 4.34 (SD = 0.758), further underscores the library's positive impact on expanding knowledge for both students and teachers. Pagalilauan et al. (2023) supported this, recognizing the library's role in fostering continuous academic engagement, enhancing research skills, and promoting critical thinking. Omeluzor et al. (2013) also emphasized the library's ability to meet evolving academic needs through its physical resources, digital tools, and research support.

The overall indicator mean of 4.42 (SD = 0.729) confirms that students highly value the library as a core academic resource. Papić and Stricević (2012) stressed the need for libraries to adapt their services to meet user needs and improve academic experiences, while Irmawati and Bakri (2022) highlighted that well-maintained, resource-rich facilities encourage greater library use. This aligns with the Expectancy-Value Theory (Drew, 2023), which posits that students are more motivated to engage with resources they perceive as valuable for academic success. The SERVQUAL Model further reinforces this by emphasizing that service quality directly impacts user satisfaction and engagement (Bhasin, 2023). Ganguly and Bhasin (2019) added that accessibility, service quality, and resource relevance shape students' library usage patterns. Technological integration and flexible learning spaces, as noted by Cha and Kim (2015), along with cultural backgrounds and individual preferences (Lizazi-Mbanga & Mapulanga, 2021), also influence engagement. Collectively, these findings highlight the importance of aligning library services with user expectations to foster academic success and sustained engagement.

The analysis of college students' overall preference for library use reveals significant insights across key indicators. The "Relevance of Library" scored a mean of 4.27 (SD = 0.791), indicating that students consider the library highly important for their academic needs. This supports Kim's (2017) assertion that libraries remain essential for academic engagement by offering adaptable learning environments. Similarly, Itsekor and Nwokeoma (2017) emphasized the library's role in promoting information dissemination,

communication, and personal development—critical factors for academic growth. The "Attitude towards Library Use" recorded a mean of 4.22 (SD = 0.794), reflecting students' positive perceptions of the library as their primary resource center. Pagalilauan et al. (2023) noted that such attitudes stem from access to spaces that cultivate critical thinking and research skills, while Irmawati and Bakri (2022) highlighted how well-equipped facilities encourage library usage. Notably, the "Valuation of the Library" achieved the highest mean score of 4.42 (SD = 0.729), underscoring the library's strong role as a primary academic resource. This aligns with Papic and Stricevic's (2012) findings on the library's importance in meeting user needs and promoting academic success.

Table 8. Overall Level of Preference of College Students

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description
Relevance of Library	4.27	0.791	Very High
Attitude towards Library Use	4.22	0.794	Very High
Valuation of the Library	4.42	0.729	Very High
Variable's Mean	4.30	0.302	Very High

The overall variable mean of 4.30 (SD = 0.302) reflects a consistently high preference for the library, resonating with the Expectancy-Value Theory (Drew, 2023), which posits that students are more motivated to use resources they find valuable and beneficial. The SERVQUAL Model (Bhasin, 2023) further explains this preference by emphasizing that service quality, accessibility, and relevance drive user satisfaction and engagement. Ganguly and Bhasin (2019) supported this by noting that aligning services with user expectations strengthens engagement and library utilization. Additionally, technological integration and flexible learning spaces play a crucial role in boosting library engagement. Cha and Kim (2015) found that modern facilities attract higher student participation, while Lizazi-Mbanga and Mapulanga (2021) emphasized that user perceptions are influenced by cultural backgrounds, academic needs, and personal preferences. These findings highlight the importance of continuously improving library services to meet evolving student expectations. Applying the Expectancy-Value Theory and SERVQUAL Model underscores the need for libraries to align resources and services with student needs, ultimately fostering deeper engagement, greater satisfaction, and sustained library use.

Level of Library Utilization

The following table shows the frequency of library use and the level of preference of college students. The results are the following:

Table 9. Level of Library Utilization Overall Result Percentage: Frequency of Library Use

Numerical Scale	Frequency	Frequency Count	Percentage
5	21 times a month and above	51	18.55%
4	16-20 times a month	89	32.36%
3	11-15 times a month	92	33.45%
2	6-10 times a month	31	11.27%
1	0-5 times in a month and below	12	4.36%

Table 9 highlights the frequency of library use among college students, revealing that most are active users. The largest group (33.45%) visits the library 11–15 times a month, closely followed by 32.36% who visit 16–20 times monthly, indicating consistent engagement with library resources. Additionally, 18.55% reported visiting 21 times or more, reflecting a segment of students who heavily rely on the library for academic purposes. In contrast, 11.27% visit 6–10 times monthly, while only 4.36% use the library 0–5 times, suggesting that while most students frequently utilize library services, a small portion engages less often. These patterns align with Ani et al. (2022), who emphasized the value of analyzing library usage trends to better understand user behavior and engagement. The data reinforces Ganguly and Bhasin's (2019) findings that frequent library visits correlate with higher student engagement and resource dependence.

The frequency of library visits also serves as a strong indicator of academic habits and success. Fagyan et al. (2023) identified frequent library use as a marker of proactive academic behavior, often linked to improved academic performance, while De Jager (2014) confirmed a positive correlation between regular library use and academic achievement. These findings underscore the library's role as a vital academic hub, fostering student development and academic growth. Recognizing these usage patterns enables administrators to optimize resources and tailor services to meet the evolving needs of students, ensuring the library continues to function as an essential support system for academic success.

Correlations Analysis between the Variables of Interest of the Study

The following table shows the correlation analysis between the variables of interest of the study with regard to library Satisfaction, Preference, and Utilization of College Students. The results are the following:

Table 10. Correlations Analysis between the Level of Satisfaction and the Level of Utilization of College Students

	Level of Library Satisfaction	Level of Library Utilization
Level of Library Satisfaction	1	.265*
Level of Library Utilization	.265*	1

The correlation coefficient of .265 between library satisfaction and utilization indicates a weak positive relationship, suggesting that while satisfaction can influence library use, it is not the primary determinant. Students may use the library frequently despite low satisfaction or visit less often even if highly satisfied. Library satisfaction reflects users' contentment with services, resources, and overall experience. Awotona and Ipadeola (2019) highlight that satisfaction extends beyond resource availability to how well resources align with academic needs. Gyau et al. (2021) identify user satisfaction as a key measure of library performance, while Younus et al. (2021) assert its influence on the frequency and depth of resource engagement. The Expectancy-Value Theory (Drew, 2023) supports this, suggesting students are more likely to use the library if they perceive it as valuable for academic and career goals. However, the weak correlation implies that additional factors beyond perceived value impact library use.

The SERVQUAL Model (Zeithaml, Berry, & Parasuraman, as cited in Bhasin, 2023) provides further insight by emphasizing service quality's role in shaping user satisfaction. Its five dimensions—reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles—affect user perceptions and engagement. Libraries that meet or exceed expectations across these dimensions foster higher satisfaction and utilization. Core services like resource access, book lending, internet use, and staff support significantly shape user experiences (Musa & Olawale, 2023), while frequently used services such as reference materials and photocopying further drive library visits (Rodrigues & Mandrekar, 2020). The library's physical environment also impacts satisfaction, with well-designed spaces promoting engagement (Iwhiwhu & Okorodudu, 2012), and inviting atmospheres encouraging frequent use (Mani et al., 2019). Moreover, a diverse and thoughtfully curated collection enhances user satisfaction and broadens appeal (Yap et al., 2022). Ashikuzzaman (2023) stresses balancing academic resources with culturally significant materials to attract varied users. In conclusion, while satisfaction affects library utilization, factors like service quality, facility design, and resource diversity play crucial roles. Academic libraries aiming to boost both satisfaction and usage must address these areas to foster deeper engagement and solidify their role as essential learning hubs.

Table 11. *Correlations Analysis between the Level of Preference and the Level of Utilization of College Students*

	<i>Level of Library Preference</i>	<i>Level of Library Utilization</i>
Level of Library Preference	1	.338*
Level of Library Utilization	.338*	1

The correlation coefficient of 0.338 between college students' library preference and utilization indicates a weak positive relationship, suggesting that while preference and usage may increase together, preference alone does not ensure frequent use. The Expectancy-Value Theory explains this by emphasizing that students' library preferences are driven by the perceived utility in achieving academic goals. Although students may value the library for studying and research, the weak correlation suggests that other factors impact actual usage. Research by Kim (2017) highlights that library preference is often shaped by perceived benefits, with administrators enhancing services to meet evolving student needs. Features such as conducive study environments, relevant resources, and supportive services can strengthen preference, yet they may not always result in consistent use, especially with the availability of convenient digital alternatives. Omeluzor et al. (2013) stress that a library's relevance, digital access, and community engagement boost student preference but may not directly increase utilization. Similarly, Cha and Kim (2015) found that while quiet spaces and technological resources attract students, personal study habits and the preference for digital tools often reduce physical library visits.

The SERVQUAL Model (Zeithaml, Berry, & Parasuraman, as cited in Bhasin, 2023) offers further insight by highlighting that service quality—measured through reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles—shapes user preferences and behaviors. Libraries that consistently meet student expectations foster stronger preferences; however, even high-quality services may not counter the appeal of more convenient online resources. Dahan et al. (2016) note that students prefer libraries aligning resources with academic and career goals, but regular use remains inconsistent. Students' attitudes and perceptions also influence this dynamic. Ganguly and Bhasin (2019) argue that modern students often favor digital platforms for information retrieval, bypassing traditional libraries, while Alokuk and Al-Amri (2021) emphasize that emotions and perceptions directly impact engagement. Rodrigues and Mandrekar (2020) found that students frequently use libraries for specific services rather than comprehensive research, reflecting selective engagement. Lizazi-Mbanga and Mapulanga (2021) further note that cultural backgrounds, academic needs, and individual preferences shape library usage. In conclusion, the weak correlation between library preference and utilization results from factors such as service quality, perceived relevance, user attitudes, and the convenience of alternatives. Applying the Expectancy-Value Theory and SERVQUAL Model reveals that preference alone cannot drive high utilization. To enhance library engagement, institutions must address motivational factors, improve service quality, and adapt to students' evolving needs, ensuring the library remains a valuable academic resource.

Regression Analysis between Variables of Interest of the Study

The following table shows the regression analysis between the variables of interest of the study with regard to library satisfaction, preference, and utilization of college students. The results are the following:

The results indicate a significant influence between library satisfaction and utilization among college students. The coefficient (B) for library satisfaction is 0.402, indicating a corresponding 0.402-unit increase in library utilization for every one-unit increase. The standardized coefficient, also known as beta, is 0.265, suggesting a weak positive relationship between these variables. In this context, statistically, with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the significance threshold of 0.05, there is a significant influence between

satisfaction and utilization. The p-value suggests a statistically significant influence between the level of satisfaction and utilization among college students; thus, this relationship may also be connected to the theoretical framework of this study.

Table 12. *Test of Influence of Library Satisfaction on Library Utilization*

Variable	B	Standardized Coefficients Beta	Standard Error	T-Value	P-Value	Alpha Value	Interpretation
Library Satisfaction	0.402	.265	0.089	4.540	.000	0.05	Significant
Constant	1.823						
Multiple R	.265	Weak Positive Correlations					
R2	.070						
Adjusted R2	.067						

According to the Expectancy-Value Theory, students likely believe that increased satisfaction with library services will lead to increased utilization (Drew, 2023). The significant relationship implies that students find utilizing the library services desirable and valuable, reinforcing their engagement. In addition, the SERVQUAL Model posits that higher satisfaction with service quality leads to continued service usage (Bhasin, 2023). The significant p-value indicates that students' satisfaction with library services meets or exceeds their expectations, increasing utilization. This alignment suggests that college students perceive the library's services as high-quality and beneficial. Because of this, college students will likely engage more, prompting them to use these services more frequently.

The Multiple R-value of 0.265 indicates a weak positive correlation between library satisfaction and utilization. This positive correlation, though weak, suggests that as students' satisfaction increases, their library utilization also increases. This aligns with the expectancy theory, as students believe that the effort to use the library will lead to a valuable outcome, reinforcing their behavior of utilizing library services. On the other hand, the standardized coefficient between satisfaction and utilization is 0.265, which suggests that utilization increases as satisfaction increases. With this, the value of 0.265 shows that the strength of this relationship is weak, meaning that while there is a positive effect, it is not particularly strong.

Despite the weak correlation, library satisfaction significantly influences library utilization. The R-squared value is 0.070, which means that satisfaction explains approximately 7% of the variability in utilization. This indicates that satisfaction statistically influences utilization but accounts for only a tiny portion of the total variability. Consequently, other factors not included in the study play a substantial role in determining utilization levels. While satisfaction positively affects utilization, it is just one of many factors influencing utilization levels among college students.

In support of this result, Wanyonyi et al. (2018) conducted a regression analysis study to determine library management strategies. Their findings suggest that libraries prioritize user satisfaction, organize essential services within specific sections and departments, understand user needs, and consistently assess user satisfaction levels. By doing so, students will use the library more frequently and take advantage of the services offered. Similarly, Padohinog (2024) emphasized the significant impact of user satisfaction on library utilization, services, and staff interactions. It stressed that user satisfaction is crucial for libraries to achieve their goals and objectives effectively.

In this context, it is suggested that libraries prioritize user satisfaction by organizing services to meet specific needs and consistently assessing satisfaction levels. Future research could explore additional factors that influence the utilization levels of college students. Understanding these factors can help libraries enhance service quality, increase user satisfaction, and improve overall performance. In conclusion, while satisfaction plays a significant role in library utilization among college students, it is just one of many factors influencing utilization levels. By addressing user satisfaction and other vital factors, libraries can improve service quality and increase utilization, ultimately enhancing the overall library experience for students.

Table 13. *Test of Influence of Library Preference on Library Utilization*

Variable	B	Standardized Coefficients Beta	Standard Error	T-Value	P-Value	Alpha Value	Interpretation
Library Preference	.565	.338	0.095	5.936	.000	0.05	Significant
Constant	1.064						
Multiple R	.338	Weak Positive Correlations					
R2	.114						
Adjusted R2	.111						

Table 13 highlights the influence of college students' preference on library utilization, showing a weak positive correlation between the two variables. The regression analysis reveals a statistically significant relationship, with a t-value of 5.936 and a p-value of .000, indicating that the results are unlikely due to chance. However, the R-squared value of 0.114 suggests that preference accounts for only 11.4% of the variance in library use, while the adjusted R-squared value of 0.111 confirms that preference alone offers only a modest estimate of utilization patterns. Despite this, preference showed a stronger influence than satisfaction, suggesting that while important, it is not the sole factor affecting library use.

These findings align with the Expectancy-Value Theory, which explains that students' decisions are shaped by their expectations of success and the value they associate with certain outcomes. Kim (2020) noted that students often use libraries for learning and information-seeking because it supports academic success. However, the weak correlation suggests that additional factors also play significant roles. Studies by Selvi (2020) and Mawia (2021) emphasized that when libraries cater to students' needs and preferences, satisfaction and usage increase. The SERVQUAL Model, used to assess service quality, further supports the idea that aligning library services with student expectations enhances utilization.

Other research highlights the importance of library environment and technology in influencing usage. Bautista (2019) found that adaptable spaces promoting both collaboration and individual study increase engagement, while Reyes and Santos (2020) identified technological integration and digital accessibility as key drivers of library use. These factors, combined with student preferences, shape library utilization. Therefore, further research is necessary to explore the complex dynamics influencing library use, ultimately guiding improvements in services and facilities to better meet students' evolving needs.

Conclusions

The study revealed that college students exhibit a very high level of library satisfaction across three key indicators—facilities, services, and collections—reflecting overall contentment with the library's features. Students also showed a strong preference for library use, particularly regarding its relevance, their attitude toward its use, and its perceived value. Frequent library visits highlight its role as a vital learning resource center, with findings indicating that both satisfaction and preference significantly influence utilization, though preference has a stronger impact. The acceptance of the alternative hypothesis—that higher satisfaction correlates with greater preference—underscores the importance of user satisfaction in shaping usage patterns. Despite a weak positive relationship between satisfaction, preference, and utilization, the study calls for further research to explore additional factors influencing library use.

To enhance student engagement, the study recommends improving technological resources, particularly by increasing computer access and ensuring fast, reliable internet connectivity. While overall satisfaction is high, these areas received lower ratings and should be prioritized. Additionally, the underutilization of the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) and online databases suggests limited student awareness, warranting reintroduction through symposiums. Faculty should also be encouraged to integrate OPAC and databases like GALE into coursework to promote regular use, potentially increasing library visits and user satisfaction. Future research should examine variables such as demographics, accessibility, and digital resource availability to gain deeper insights into library utilization and inform strategies for service enhancement.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Earl Benedict A. Bawasanta

St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. – Philippines

Jeraldine F. Apal

St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. – Philippines

Mae A. Bolasa

St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. – Philippines

Julia Claire A. Lumanta

St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. – Philippines

Kenneth Mesario

St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. – Philippines

Emmanuel L. Templa, MPA

St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. – Philippines

Dr. Katherine Rosales

St. Peter's College of Toril, Inc. – Philippines